

Language infrastructures in support of text mining

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we describe a generic language resources infrastructure providing language data and language processing services, as well as different instances of the infrastructure catering for different communities, operational frameworks and constraints. We maintain that similar approaches can be employed to support and systematize the storage, documentation, archiving and long-term maintenance of scientific publications, as well as their discoverability, uniform access and processing through interoperable text mining services, and conclude with a discussion of the merits of the approach.

CCS Concepts

- **Information systems** → **Digital libraries and archives**
- **Applied computing** → **Document management and text processing**

Keywords

language resources; language resources infrastructures; text mining; language processing services

1. INTRODUCTION

Text mining tools and services process unstructured textual data in order to extract meaningful information contained in the text. Whether aiming at sentiment extraction based on customers' views on products from open-ended survey responses or from social media texts, messages, etc., or at automatic classification of texts in order to support the routing of documents to the appropriate recipients, or at clustering free-text descriptions by patients of their symptoms in order to extract clues facilitating diagnosis, or to extract information from scientific publications, or any other goal, the main type of object to be processed, or mined, is unstructured textual data.

The analysis of such types of data, notably including scientific publications, from the language point of view, presents manifold challenges; indicatively:

- The identification of the appropriate sources of content requests the utilization of several tools during the stage of

aggregation and pre-processing of the data (e.g. web crawlers, language identifiers, cleanup tools, text normalizers, etc.).

- The case of data with insufficient, erroneous or no metadata, and vice versa, metadata with no available (due to a number of reasons) full text data is not infrequent.
- The identification of appropriate data which are, however, in non-processable formats (such as non-processable pdf or image) imposes the need for further processing, e.g. optical character recognition or ad hoc converters.
- Interoperability issues quite often cause problems to the text mining process, in the case of non-compatibility of data and tools or of tools to each other; this hinders the construction of workflows and demands the development of conversion tools.
- Existing systems have been trained on different types of data or on other languages, domains and text types than the ones aimed at, thus, making their adjustment to the specific needs indispensable, although challenging.
- Finally, besides technical issues, text mining faces legal challenges when dealing with non-open data, or data with unclear licensing conditions. Even the case of open data or public data suffers from uncertainty as to the lawfulness of use, given the diversity of legal frameworks, especially in the EU.

In this paper we focus on generic but useful existing solutions that attempt to address some of these hindrances in what concerns the necessary general language-related infrastructural aspects of text mining, including mining of scientific publications. We describe four different instantiations of language resources infrastructures, trying to address the specific requirements of each endeavor in the framework of which they were developed, namely, with and without integrating processing services, local or cloud-based deployment, catering for expert or non-expert users, for public sector data or not.

We claim that an approach based on similar principles would be appropriate for scientific publications mining; by principles we refer to: treatment of (collections of) publications as a specific type of LRs; deployment of a "meta-infrastructure" to support mining of scientific publications by harvesting existing infrastructures; mapping of existing documentation on a common metadata schema; facilitation of the creation of user-defined resources as well as language processing tools and workflows tailored to text and data mining; finally, provision of clear access rights.

2. CREATING A GENERIC LANGUAGE RESOURCES INFRASTRUCTURE

The very diverse and heterogeneous landscape of huge amounts of digital and digitized collections has drastically transformed the requirements for their identification, discovery, archiving, long-

term maintenance, but also their processing with tools, services and applications for the purposes of linguistic analysis and annotation, text mining included. To address these requirements concerning all stages of the life-cycle of digital textual collections, as well as to cater for the observed fragmented landscape of data and services provision, we propose the use of specifically designed language resources infrastructures, comprising datasets and language processing tools as well as workflows.

Such a resource infrastructure, allowing easy sharing of data and tools, ensuring interoperability at different levels and complying with the principles of open data and open science, could constitute an important step in meeting these requirements. Digital repositories provide the infrastructure for describing and documenting, storing, preserving, and making language (notably textual) data publicly available in an open, user-friendly and trusted way. Repositories represent an evolution of the digital libraries paradigm, offering advanced search capabilities, and being deployable on large-scale distributed computing and storage environments. Aggregators, such as CORE (<https://core.ac.uk/>) [Knoth 2012] and OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>), to name just two of the initiatives that strongly support open access, collect data from and provide access to many different sources (publication and dataset repositories, journals, CRIS systems and other databases). Critical for such endeavors is the issue of metadata harmonization, since various sources adhere to different models having different metadata elements, or even same element names but different semantics, as, for example, "date" used to refer to creation date or to publication date, "language" being a free text field or based on a controlled vocabulary, e.g. iso639.

2.1 Language Resources (LRs)

The term *language resource* (LR) encompasses both datasets (textual, multimodal/multimedia and lexical data, grammars, language models etc.) and tools/technologies/services used for their processing. The focus of LR is on the set rather than the unit (e.g. not on a single text/audio file, in the case of corpora, or word/entry, in the case of lexica). In this sense, a collection of thousands of publications in a specific domain (e.g. life-sciences) would be one single resource of considerable size, but still, just a single homogeneous resource or dataset. An indicative such example is the ACL Anthology Reference Corpus [Bird et al. 2008], a corpus of scholarly publications on the subject of computational linguistics. This view on publications can be contrasted to the libraries' approach, whereby each single book, journal or article needs to maintain its identity, even if it participates in larger collections.

LRs are mainly viewed as material for language study, as training data and testbeds for language processing tools and technologies, for language modeling etc., the focus being on the language rather than on the content per se; recently, however, the use of LR has attracted other research communities, from the biomedical domain to the social sciences and humanities.

Classification of LR relies on sets of type-dependent features, which allow the viewing of the same resource along multiple dimensions. Thus, for instance, language can be used as an organizing feature to bring together corpora according to their linguality (monolingual, multilingual, comparable corpora); additionally, their subject domain, format, annotation level (e.g. morphological or syntactical annotation of corpora) can be used as different dimensions according to which an inventory of LR can be structured and later on accessed.

Despite differences, many similarities are observed between LR and publications as regards their availability, documentation, discoverability, maintenance and accessibility. The scattered publications landscape with publications located at publishers' websites, libraries, repositories and personal pages is also observed in the case of LR. The need for stable and reliable structures providing storage, documentation and access to LR becomes imperative. An infrastructure trying to meet these goals has been developed in the framework of different projects, following slightly varying implementations, each one catering for the needs of different communities and focusing on different aspects of LR collection and processing, as well as meeting different operational constraints. These implementations, namely META-SHARE, QT21, CLARIN and ELRC-SHARE, will be presented in the following sections.

2.2 Language resources infrastructure for language technology development

A Europe-wide attempt was initiated in 2011 to treat the fragmentation in the domain of language technology in what concerns the availability of clearly documented, easily accessible, lawfully downloadable and re-usable LR. Although the field of language technology had seen initiatives on collecting, archiving and distributing LR, such as the ELRA (<http://www.elra.info/en/>) and the LDC (<https://catalog.ldc.upenn.edu/>) catalogues, this attempt aimed to actively involve resource providers and consumers in a common, resource sharing network, aiming to provide a uniform catalogue of various LR from different sources, to ease discovery but also to facilitate access.

META-SHARE (<http://www.meta-share.org>), an open resource exchange infrastructure, is a pan-European network of distributed repositories of LR [Piperidis 2012]. Currently, it consists of 27 repositories, making available 2732 resources (datasets and tools). It offers providers and consumers of resources the necessary functionalities for describing, storing, searching, licensing and downloading LR in a single integrated technical platform. META-SHARE promotes the growing open data and open tools and services movement. It contains language data and tools documented with high-quality metadata according to the specially designed metadata schema and aggregated in inventories allowing for uniform search and access.

Organizations participating in the META-SHARE network set up their own repositories by using the respective repository software centrally provided (<https://github.com/metashare/META-SHARE>), to store and provide access to their own resources. Selected repositories, besides providing access to their own resources, are also used as storage and documentation facilities for donated or orphan resources. Resources and their metadata reside in the repositories, which expose metadata records for harvesting. Harvested metadata are stored and indexed in central servers which constitute the entry points into the networked infrastructure.

2.2.1 Documentation of LR s

The META-SHARE metadata model [Gavrilidou et al. 2012] comprises elements and relations required for the description of LR, organized in components (according to the Component Metadata Initiative, CMDI [Broeder et al 2012]), and covering datasets as well as tools and services. The model includes identification information (resource name, type, language, etc.), administration information (creation, distribution, licensing), technical information (format, size, encoding etc.), but also information on resource production and usage. Four types of

resources are distinguished: corpora, lexical/conceptual resources, tools/services and language descriptions. For reasons of functionality and interoperability, the principle of a minimal core subset of metadata was introduced: the elements that form this minimal set are indispensable for LR description and are *obligatory*. Interoperability between datasets and language processing tools and services, as well as interoperability with other schemas and typologies is guaranteed at this minimal level of description. The schema also includes *recommended* and *optional* components and elements. Linking of related resources, such as original and derived, raw and annotated resources, a dataset and the tool that has been used to create it, is also provided. Currently, the schema has been implemented as an XML schema (XSD) and as RDF/OWL [McCrae et al 2015]. In the META-SHARE taxonomy, a distinction is made between a LR per se (core entity) and all other related entities (satellite entities), such as documents related to or describing the resource (e.g. publications, reports, manuals etc.), persons and organizations involved (e.g. creators, funders, distributors etc.), related projects and activities (e.g. funding projects, etc.) and licenses for sharing and distribution of LRs.

2.2.2 Licensing of resources

Crucial for the use of a resource is the precise documentation of the rights of use of a dataset, tool or service. The META-SHARE licensing scheme is organized on the axes of Creative Commons licenses and variations of them (specifically defined by META-SHARE) for datasets, and existing standard open source software (FOSS) licenses for tools and services. The rights and restrictions of use of the resource are under the control of the resource owners. Metadata elements documenting the rights of use are obligatory (no resource can be deposited in the infrastructure without license metadata). Consequently, users can promptly understand what they are allowed to do with a specific resource.

3. EXTENDING THE INFRASTRUCTURE WITH A LANGUAGE PROCESSING LAYER

META-SHARE has been used as the LR sharing platform for a number of initiatives, among which the QTLaunchPad project (<http://www.qt21.eu/launchpad/>) focusing on machine translation and the Greek CLARIN infrastructure (<http://www.clarin.gr>) focusing primarily on social sciences and humanities but extending to all scientific domains.

To relieve language processing and text mining users from the burden and complexity of looking for, installing and learning to use relevant language processing tools, the primary repository functionalities have been extended by *providing an additional language processing mechanism* for the processing of language datasets with appropriate tools. Language processing tools are documented with the appropriate metadata in the repository (<http://qt21.metashare.ilsp.gr/>) and are provided as web services through the *language processing (LP)* layer. In a typical usage scenario, when a user selects to process a dataset, a list of all available *relevant* processing services (e.g. tokenization & sentence splitting, POS tagging, lemmatization, dependency parsing, named entity recognition, or even text alignment in case of multilingual corpora) is automatically generated, relevance being based on the properties of the dataset, i.e. its resource type, language(s), domain, format, annotation level, and licensing conditions. Thus, an English parser appears in the list of applicable tools if syntactical analysis of English texts is needed, while a part-of-speech tagger for Portuguese appears when context to be processed is Portuguese. As

soon as the user selects a service, the server dispatches the dataset to the specific web service(s) for processing. When the processing has been completed, the new (annotated) dataset is automatically stored and indexed in the repository, thus supporting its organic growth. Thus, for example, named entities (person names, organization names, etc.) extracted from a corpus will form a new, derivative resource stored in the repository. Indicatively, protein names extracted from a biomedical resource could be used to create a new lexical resource, which, in turn could be used to annotate other textual resources, facilitating their classification in the biomedical domain.

In view of integrating the LP layer, the existing data infrastructure and the supporting software were adapted: (a) the metadata model was extended to document LP services as well as processing-related properties of datasets (based on which the selection of the appropriate tools is performed), and (b) mechanisms were developed for automatically creating the metadata records of the newly generated datasets as a result of processing. Automatic creation of metadata records for newly-created datasets combines the metadata descriptions of the original dataset and the language processing tool/service used; it also creates relations between the original dataset and the annotated one.

The workflows of the LP layer are implemented based on a variety of natural language processing services. These services can run either locally within the application environment, or they can be accessed via remote services. Details on how workflows are modelled and their implementation are presented in [Piperidis et al 2015]. Considering the language processing operations from the legal framework point of view, we have until now adopted a simplified operational model by which only openly licensed, without a no-derivatives restriction, datasets can be processed by openly licensed services and workflows.

4. INFRASTRUCTURE OF LR'S FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

The clarin:el infrastructure is the Greek part of the European CLARIN infrastructure (www.clarin.eu), a pan-European network of organizations for the collection, documentation, curation and distribution of LRs and language processing web services mainly targeting the field of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). Today, the European network counts more than 145 members from 18 countries.

In this framework, a slightly different approach to the infrastructure has been adopted, dictated by the requirement to cater for the needs of a different user community, SSH researchers, with no knowledge of language technology. Unlike the fully (technically and operationally) distributed architecture in the META-SHARE network, the clarin:el approach centralizes the creation, management and administration of repositories, thus taking the burden of local hosting from member-organizations wishing to set up an institutional LR's repository. Repositories are automatically set up on ~okeanos (<https://okeanos.grnet.gr/home/>), the research cloud infrastructure of the Greek Research and Technology Network and actual datasets are stored in its distributed permanent storage pithos+ (<https://okeanos.grnet.gr/services/pithos/>). Resources are persistently identified using handles (www.handle.net) upon being published in the repositories. LP services are also deployed on the cloud infrastructure and are centrally managed and certified.

5. PUBLIC SECTOR DATA AS LRs

Realizing the potential of public sector data for language technology research but also as object of study using text mining tools, we have recently set up a similar instance of a repository-based infrastructure for public sector data. This instance, ELRC-SHARE (<https://elrc-share.ilsp.gr/>), features an adapted simplified metadata model, essentially a pruned version of the fully-fledged schema described in section 2.2.1 above, albeit enriched with appropriate controlled vocabularies for e.g. domain classification to accommodate the widespread use of EuroVoc (<http://eurovoc.europa.eu/>) as a standard multilingual classification thesaurus among documentation services in the public sector of EU Member States. Similarly, controlled vocabularies for legal metadata elements include a range of open government licenses. Last, addressing public sector officers has necessitated simplifying the forms of access and the modalities employed for documenting public data contributed as language resources in the repository.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a generic LR infrastructure providing language data and language processing services, as well as different instances of the infrastructure catering for different communities, operational frameworks and constraints. We maintain that similar approaches can be employed for systematizing the use of text mining services for mining scientific publications. Such an approach should build bridges to existing infrastructures for aggregating and providing access to scientific publications, like OpenAIRE and CORE.

A typical scenario in this approach would entail the following steps: using filters offered by the specially designed interface of the infrastructure, the user requests (collections of) publications harvested from publication aggregators based on harmonized metadata schemas; the retrieved publications constitute a corpus; publications' metadata are percolated to the corpus level; the user selects text and data mining workflows from the available list to process the corpus; the available workflows have been previously created in the same way, i.e. formed by the combination of interoperable components from various sources; processing results are in turn fed into the infrastructure for future use by all users.

Advantages such an approach could offer for text mining of scientific publications include:

- establishing the use of scholarly publications as a type of LR, either as single texts or as collections of texts bundled together based on a given parameter (domain, language, publisher, etc.);
- promoting the documentation of such resources with richer metadata and enabling the bridging and mapping of metadata, paving the way to interoperability. The current practice for publications' metadata does not include specific elements for their processability by text mining or natural language processing tools; the proposed change in perspective (i.e. viewing publications as a specific type of LRs) will entail the enrichment of existing metadata models with the appropriate elements, facilitating, thus, the deployment of language technology for mining of publications;
- enhancing the potential of bringing together publications, datasets, tools and workflows in a user-friendly way, enabling the application of the most appropriate language processing service/workflow for the desired annotation;
- accommodating licensing issues in a clear and documented manner, safeguarding the lawful use of resources.

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